

SUSTAINABLE FAÇADE APPROACHES IN URBAN CONSERVATION AREAS

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Abstract: The world is facing an ever-increasing need for energy. In order to meet the energy needs, to use and manage the resources correctly, the development of sustainable energy efficient design approaches in all areas has gained importance and speed (Yeniay and Arpaçuoğlu, 2020). In 1972, at the United Nations Conference, the concept of sustainability emerged for the first time in the sense of "being" (Erşan and Demirarslan, 2020). The relationship between the sustainable approach, the main purpose of which is the balanced use of the environment and natural resources, and the relationship between architecture, produces structures that are compatible with the conditions and culture of the geography where they are located, and take into account the comfort of life; at the same time, it is to take care of the needs of future generations (Arslan, 2023). In architecture, a sustainable approach was followed in the creation of the built environment until the industrial revolution, using traditional resources and natural methods and materials. However, after the industrial revolution, the growth of cities accelerated, and with the increase in population, the consumption of resources accelerated and has survived to the present day (Passion, 2015). Globally, 50% of energy resource consumption and 42% of water are consumed in the built environment and construction activities, and 50% of greenhouse gas emissions, 40% of drinking water pollution and 24% of air pollution consist of construction activities (Tutku and İmamoğlu, 2015). In this context, it is a necessity to revise the existing building stock in the built environment with sustainable design and to design new buildings in line with the principles of sustainability in our world, which is facing an energy crisis.

Keywords: Sustainable Façade, Urban Protected Area and Sustainable Façade, New Sustainable Facades in Conservation Areas.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world is facing an ever-increasing need for energy. In order to meet the energy needs, to use and manage the resources correctly, the development of sustainable energy efficient design approaches in all areas has gained importance and speed (Yeniay and Arpaçuoğlu, 2020). In 1972, at the United Nations Conference, the concept of sustainability emerged for the first time in the sense of "being" (Erşan and Demirarslan, 2020). The relationship between the sustainable approach, the main purpose of which is the balanced use of the environment and natural resources, and the relationship between architecture, produces structures that are compatible with the conditions and culture of the geography where they are located, and take into account the comfort of life; at the same time, it is to take care of the needs of future generations (Arslan, 2023).

In architecture, a sustainable approach was followed in the creation of the built environment until the industrial revolution, using traditional resources and natural methods and materials. However, after the industrial revolution, the growth of cities accelerated, and with the increase in population, the consumption of resources accelerated and has survived to the present day (Passion, 2015). Globally, 50% of energy resource consumption and 42% of water are consumed in the built environment and construction activities, and 50% of greenhouse gas emissions, 40% of drinking water pollution and 24% of air pollution consist of construction activities (Tutku and İmamoğlu, 2015).

In this context, it is a necessity to revise the existing building stock in the built environment with sustainable design and to design new buildings in line

with the principles of sustainability in our world, which is facing an energy crisis.

Urban protected areas are surrounded by new structures in cities built today. Although the urban protected area legislations that affect and guide sustainable building and façade designs are not sufficient and explanatory, they differ according to the areas where they are located (Toprak, 2020). The stock of today's buildings in historical areas is substantial. For example, while the number of registered buildings in 40 parcels in Tuzla Köyiçi is 116, the number of new building facades that look at the historical building and must be approved by the conservation boards to which it is affiliated is around 1016 (Tuzla municipality, 2021).

As can be understood from this example, the lack of clarity in the sustainable design criteria of the 1016 building causes the sustainability approach in the design to be pushed into the background and the sustainable design of the contractor to be abandoned by considering the uncertainty of the bureaucratic process (Akropol, 2022).

Considering the historical cities, protected areas and other conservation zones in our geography, it would not be wrong to say that an important new building stock is far from the understanding of energy efficient and sustainable design. Sustainable construction in urban protected areas and conservation areas, and parameter deficiencies in façade design decisions bring along a serious resource consumption (Enç, 2009).

In this context, when the literature was scanned, 15,000 studies under the title of "sustainable façade", 13,800 studies under the title of "sustainable façade systems" and 1,960 studies, 28 of which were articles, were scanned under the title of "sustainable façade

approaches in urban protected areas" in Google Academy.

In addition, when we search under the headings of "Urban protected areas", "Tuzla", "Sustainable façade approaches", 155 studies are seen. The vast majority of the 155 studies are related to large-scale decision-making mechanisms in urban protected areas and conservation zones, and studies on sustainable façade and building designs are scarce.

In the literature review, with the examination of building forms and application methods in historical areas (Eren, 1986). He has a study on the factors affecting new architectural design processes in conservation areas (Velioglu, 1992). The effects of new buildings in conservation areas on the silhouette and the deficiencies of legal regulations are emphasized (Baydarlioğlu, 1994). He has studies on the problems of new building designs in historical areas (Karabağ, 1997), (Aydın, 1998), (Karakul, 2002), (Kaynarca, 2003), (Bilgiç, 2004), (İdil, Kanat, Duralı, 2007), (Enç, 2009). After 2010, it is seen that the studies focus on sustainable new building designs in historical areas. Working with sustainable shell designs of new structures in conservation areas (Düzgün, 2010).

Study on the problems of new construction in the historical environment (Can, 2011).

In the studies, it has been seen that there are very few sustainable new building and façade works in historical conservation areas, the problem has been identified by emphasizing the sources of the problem throughout the studies, it has been seen that sustainable façade systems have not been examined and the parameters of adding to the designs in protected areas have not been studied.

Within the scope of this study, it is aimed to develop sustainable façade approaches in new building facades in urban protected areas in the built environment and to increase the applicability of façade decisions that play a role in reducing energy and resource consumption in protected areas.

2. CRITERIA IN BUILDING DESIGN IN URBAN PROTECTED AREAS

Law No. 5226 on the Protection of Cultural and Natural Heritage, "Protected areas, areas within the built environment with the development of the city; He says that the historical buildings, elements of artistic value, gardens, walls facing the street and natural covers in

these areas are meaningful with all the elements that make up a whole and should be protected as a whole (2016). From the past to the present, the definitions and scope of protection have developed and changed. Today, conservation approaches, which are also evaluated within the scope of sustainable environment, have been evaluated together with building, built environment, geographical culture and effective energy improvement studies for many years around the world.

2.1. Development of urban protected areas and conservation approach.

In 2005, at the World Heritage and Contemporary Architecture Meeting Towards New Conservation Standards organized by UNESCO; Although it is stated that the contemporary architectural works around the Cologne Cathedral in the German State of North Rhine-Westphalia may pose a danger, it is emphasized in the conclusion that the developments in historical cities should be sustainable and that the search for ways should be started to ensure that only modern infrastructure and facilities are invested without harming the social ones. cultural and economic assets that are the heritage value of the city (UNESCO, 2005).

It is necessary to look at the understanding of conservation and sustainable construction and environmental development from past to present in Turkey. In this context, when the researches were examined, the data obtained from (Dinçer, Akin, 1994), (Tekeli, 1998), (Bektaş, 1992), (Osmay, 1998), (Bilgin, 1998), (Akozan, 1977), (Akçura, 1972) and other studies were tabulated and in "Table 1", it was aimed to reveal the evolution of urban protected area, conservation approach and sustainability chronologically.

Despite modern urban planning approaches to the problems brought by industrialization and industrial cities in Europe, the prevention of fires in Ottoman cities and the concern of new settlements guided the plans. In the 1910s, many monuments were centralized, with the evacuation and focus of large monuments.

It is seen that the city-scale protection laws and regulations legalized in Turkey intensified between 1950 and 1980 (Bektaş, 1992). The 1950s are considered by academic circles as the turning point of the understanding of conservation (Dinçer, 1994).

Table:1 Chronological table showing the important developments of urban conservation in world history.

Important Evolution Points of the International Protection Approach		
14.yüzyıl	İTALYA	Of artists and humanists. Thanks to his interest and admiration for the ancient period, it seems that conservation awareness has begun to emerge.
15.yüzyıl 16.yüzyıl	İTALYA	Papa Nicolaus V. / He initiated the preparation of a list of historical monuments in Rome. The positive impact of his work spread throughout Italy.
17.yüzyıl	AVRUPA	The period in which documents related to historical artifacts are collected, classified and evaluated.
18.yüzyıl	AVRUPA	The period when my rational and normative approaches came to the fore
19.yüzyıl	FRANSA	Eugène Emmanuel Viollet-le-Duc (1814-1879) She Emphasized the "Unity of Style Approach" and restorations. He wrote a 10-volume history of architecture, "Dictionary of Rational Architecture".
	İNGİLTERE	Sir Gilbert Squatland / Viollet-le-Duc was the pioneer of the unity of style approach as an approach to the preservation of historical buildings in England.
	AVRUPA	After 1850, the conservation approach in Europe was made with this understanding.
	İNGİLTERE	John Rustin, Giulian Morris and Others. / In England, they published the "1877 Manifesto" on behalf of STAF, the Society for the Protection of Ancient Monuments; "The building's documentary qualities are being destroyed for its style and SIT integrity. There should be conservation instead of restoration." The concept of classical protectionism was first introduced by John Rustin and Gulian Morris. The concept of protection began to develop slowly.

In the table that is a continuation of Table:1, the chronological table of the development of historical buildings and urban conservation in Turkey is given. Tabulated by the author, 2024.

2.2. New Building Design and Sustainable Facade Criteria in Urban Protected Areas

In cases where new building designs are in question in historical environments, there is both a design and conservation problem. The conservation approach is generally perceived as a concept against the new (Kuçak Toprak, 2020). Many property owners, individuals, companies, designers avoid using conservation concepts at the same time as new designs. Perhaps they see the concept of conservation as an independent, discrete activity that does not involve design, or as a judgment on the endangerment of the architectural fabric of the historic environment as specified in the conservation standards. Architects who restore a historic building, establish a new function, or construct a new building in a historic setting know that this is a misunderstanding. In cases where the purpose of the project is not just protection, a large number of design decisions can be developed to ensure successful conservation or to prevent the tissue from being threatened (Mills, 2002).

Without avoiding innovations in the designs made to fulfill the requirements of sustainability, trying to

protect the historical environment and integrating it for certain purposes will be different in each society; however, research shows that historical cities have to meet with the new in terms of function and structure (Kuçak Toprak, 2020).

Over the years, new building design approaches have been formed in urban protected areas, universal decisions and declarations have been put forward; When the researches in this context are examined (Historic England, 2008), (Bonatz, 1943), (The Charter of Krakow, 2000), (Icomos, 1996), (ICOMOS, 1972b), (Commission for Architecture and the Built Environment (CABE) & English Heritage, 2007), (Historic Scotland; 7, 11, 2010), (Kuç, 2020), (Kanat, 2007), (Zeren and Tanaç, 2019), (Conservation Development Plan, 2018), (Ergenç, 1986), (Velioglu, 1992), (Baydarlıoğlu, 1992), (Kaynarca, 2003), (Bilgiç, 2004), (Aydın, 1998), (Eraslan, 2022), (Düzgün, 2010) and other studies were tabulated and universal design criteria were tried to be revealed in "Table 2".

Important Evolution Points of the International Protection Approach	
19.yüzyıl	ITALYA Camillo Boito 1883'te / He explained the basic principles called "5 Principles of Contemporary Restoration"
20.yüzyıl	HINDİSTAN Bop Kuruz 1910-15 (Hindistan Vallisi) / It reveals the monuments by destroying the built environment surrounding the monuments in India. This approach is called the "Haussmann" approach. It has been applied in many parts of the world. The surroundings of Hagia Sophia were also designed with this approach (İlhan, 2005).
	ITALYA After the 1920s, research, theories and approach development on conservation gained momentum.
	ITALYA CARTA DEL RESTAURO (1931) / In Italy, conservation and restoration theories emerge as a system. It is described as the "First Constitution of Restoration".
	ATINA 1931' de in Athens / CARTA DEL RESTAURO principles were adopted at the International Congress of Architects and Technicians of Historical Monuments.
	AVRUPA There were differences in conservation approaches and practices during World War II. (the need for shelter after demolition and the repair approaches of destroyed monuments) have emerged.
	AVRUPA London1945 / A decision was taken by 44 countries regarding the establishment of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). UNESCO was established in 1946.
AVRUPA Paris 1957 / Paris Congress (International Congress of Architects and Technicians of Historical Monuments)	

Table 2: New construction and sustainable façade criteria in urban conservation zones created from universal design approaches. Tabulated by the author, 2024.

		Kentsel Sit Alanlarında Yeni Yapı Tasarımı ve Sürdürülebilir Cephe Kriteri																											
		Fiziksel Çevre Kontrolü				Ölçek / Kütle				Tarihi Silüette Uyumu ve Devamlılığı				Cephe Form Yaklaşımı				Kendi Dönemine Ait Malzeme ve Teknik Yaklaşımı				Ritim			Tarihi kent Peyzajına Uyumluluğu		Fonksiyon		
		TOPOGRAFYA	RÜZGAR	GÜNEŞ	YAGIŞ	YUKSEKLİK	SACAĞAK BOYU	KÜTLE	PENCERE ORAN	KAPI ORAN	YAPI ÇEKİMİ	Dönem Farkı	USLUP TEZATLİĞİ	TASARIM BASKIN OLMAMALI	FORM	BALKON	DERİN BÖLMELER	ÇIKMA	GELENEKSEL MALZEME	DOKU	RENK	KAPLAMA	İNSAN ÖLÇEĞİ	ZEMİN KAT SOKAK İLİSKİSİ	SOKAK RİTİMİ	YOLLARA UYUMLU	PEYZAJA UYGUN	YAY-DOLAŞIM AKSINA UYGUN	YAPILŞEV UYUMU
1	Kuşçak Toprak, Gizem 2020	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	
2	Kanat, 2007.	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	○	○	
3	Zeren, Mine Tanaç, 2019	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	○	✓	○	○	○	○	✓	○	○
4	21641 sayılı Koruma Amaçlı İmar Planı Teknik Şartnamesi 2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○
5	Ergen . 1986.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○
6	Velioğlu .1992.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	✓	○	○	✓	○	○	✓	○	○	○
7	Baydarlıoğlu. 1992	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
8	Karabağ .1997.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
9	Aydın . 1998.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○
10	Karakul . 2002.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○
11	Kaynarca. 2003.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
12	Bilgiç. 2004.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○

Table 2: Continued. Tabulated by the author, 2024

Kentsel Sit Alanlarında Yeni Yapı Tasarımı ve Sürdürülebilir Cephe Kriteri																																
	Fiziksel Çevre Kontrolü				Ölçek / Kütle				Tarihi Silüette Uyum ve Devamlılığı				Cephe Form Yaklaşım				Kendi Dönemine Ait Malzeme ve Teknik Yaklaşımı				Ritim				Tarihi kent Peyzajına Uyumlu				Fonksiyon			
	TOPOGRAFYA	RÜZGAR	GÜNEŞ	YAĞIŞ	YÜKSEKLİK	SAÇAK BOYU	KÜTLE	PENCERE ORAN	KAPI ORAN	YAPI ÇEKİMESİ	Dönem Farkı	USLUP TEZATLIĞI	TASARIM BASKIN OLMAMALI	FORM	BALKON	DERİN BÖLMELER	ÇIKMA	GELENEKSEL MALZEME	DOKU	RENK	KAPLAMA	İNSAN ÖLÇEĞİ	ZEMİN KAT SOKAK İLİŞKİSİ	SOKAK RİTİMİ	YOLLARA UYUMLU	PEYZAJA UYGUN	YAYA-DOLAŞIM AKSINA UYGUN	YAPI İŞLEV UYUMU				
13	Eraslan, 2022	✓	✓	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	✓					
14	Enç, 2009.	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	○	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○					
15	Düvgün, 2010.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
16	Can, 2011.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
17	Groat, 1983.	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
18	Kurrent, 2001.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
19	UNESCO Yeni Koruma Standartlarına Doğru Dünya Miras ve Çağdaş Mimari Toplantı Notları, 2005.	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
20	ICOMOS, 1972b	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
21	Çelen Gök, Demet, 2016.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
22	Commission for Architecture and the Built Environment (CABE) & English Heritage, 2007.	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
23	Preservation Alliance for Greater Philadelphia, 22, 2007.	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					
24	Asia Pacific Heritage Awards for Culture Heritage Conservation (UNESCO, 2008)	✓	✓	✓	○	○	✓	✓	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○					

Table 3: Table showing the percentage ratios of new building and sustainable façade criteria in urban conservation zones created from universal design approaches. Tabulated by the author, 2024.

Kentsel Sit Alanlarında Yeni Yapı Tasarımı ve Sürdürülebilir Cephe Kriteri Yüzdelik Değerlendirme (%)																												
Fiziksel Çevre Kontrolü	Ölçek / Kütle				Tarihi Silüette Uyum ve Devamlılığı				Cephe Form Yaklaşım				Kendi Dönemine Ait Malzeme ve Teknik Yaklaşımı				Ritim				Tarihi kent Peyzajına Uyumlu				Fonksiyon			
	TOPOGRAFYA	RÜZGAR	GÜNEŞ	YAĞIŞ	YÜKSEKLİK	SAÇAK BOYU	KÜTLE	PENCERE ORAN	KAPI ORAN	YAPI ÇEKİMESİ	DÖNEM FARKI	USLUP TEZATLIĞI	TASARIM BASKIN OLMAMALI	FORM	BALKON	DERİN BÖLMELER	ÇIKMA	GELENEKSEL MALZEME	DOKU	RENK	KAPLAMA	İNSAN ÖLÇEĞİ	ZEMİN KAT SOKAK İLİŞKİSİ	SOKAK RİTİMİ	YOLLARA UYUMLU	PEYZAJA UYGUN	YAYA-DOLAŞIM AKSINA UYGUN	YAPI İŞLEV UYUMU
100	100	100	100	83	100	79,2	100	100	100	95,8	83,3	66,7	87,5	100	83,3	50	75	58,3	95,8	75	75	100	54,2	50	79,2	70,8	50	41,7

Figure 1: Graph showing the percentages of sustainable façade criteria. Prepared by the author, 2024.

Table 2 Injured New Building Design and Sustainable Facade Criteria Value Description Physical Environmental Control

Topography: Buildings must be designed according to their geography and topographic features. A good reading of environmental features and integrating them into the design ensures that all physical conditions and the improvement properties of physical conditions are used in the building.

Wind, Sun, Precipitation: These are important parameters in designs in order to transfer the microclimate effect to the design in a positive way and to benefit from sustainable natural effects.

. Scale/Mass

Height-eaves length-mass-door, window ratios: These are the design criteria that affect the sustainability values of new buildings to be built not only in areas where historical buildings are located, but also in the entire built environment. They are the building parts that shape the energy requirement ratios. **Harmony and continuity in its historical skyline**

Structural Attractiveness-Period Difference-Stylistic Contrast: The continuity of the silhouette is the parameters that provide the visual and physical continuity necessary for the holistic preservation of the historical texture.

Facade Formwork Approach

Form: The form approach in new buildings and silhouettes near historical buildings can also be defined as the shape and pattern of the building envelope.

Deep partitions-Balcony-Overhang: These are pieces of street fabric that need to be protected. During the use of these elements, which give character to the street, in new buildings, the street must be read well.

Understanding of material and technical construction of his period

3. FIELDWORK

3.1. Study Area and Sample Selection.

Within the scope of this study, Station Street, which is located in 40 parcels of Köyiçi, which is located in the "Tuzla Urban Protected Area" in Istanbul, was selected. The selection of the area was influenced by the fact that registered buildings and today's new buildings form the whole of the street silhouette. The facades of the buildings approved by the relevant conservation board on İstiklal Street will be examined in terms of sustainable façade design criteria and applicable façade decision parameters will be established.

18 new buildings and 3 registered buildings are important criteria in the selection of the street section;

- They have different floor heights.
- Having a mixed function (Commercial-residential)
- Distance to registered buildings mlayon
- differentiation of esafes.
- Variety in façade materials.
- Differences in the form of the façade (overhang-balcony-corner overhangs, etc.).
- Changes in roof shapes.
- They are suitable for the creation of the street silhouette and for rhythm evaluation;

In this study; Urban protected areas in Turkey, chronology of conservation approach legislation, new building designs in protected areas, universal and decision criteria will be examined. The examined criteria will be evaluated and tabulated in line with the decisions of the sustainable façade approach.

3.2. Tuzla-Köyiçi Mevki Station Street design approved by the Conservation Board; Create an identity assessment.

Table 4: Table of identification information for damaged new buildings on İstiklal Street. Tabulated by the author, 2024.

04	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Fibercement
05	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Precast Contour
06	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Precast Contour
07	REGISTERED BUILDING					
08	Reinforced concrete	2	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
09	Reinforced concrete	2	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint
10	Reinforced concrete	2	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
11	Reinforced concrete	2	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
12	Reinforced concrete	2	Residential Commercial	Trade	Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
13	REGISTERED BUILDING					

All of the new buildings in the study area are built with a reinforced concrete vehicle system. The usage function of the street is included in the plans as Residential and Commercial (Tuzla Municipality,

2018). The new buildings next to the registered building are built as 2 floors, while the other new buildings are seen as 3 floors.

Table 4: Continued; Table of identification information for damaged new buildings on Istiklal Street. Tabulated by the author, 2024.

İSTASYON CADDESİ

	Carrier System	Number of Floors	Function	Ground Usage	Floor	Upstairs Usage	Facade Cladding
14	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint
15	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint
16	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
17	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
18	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
19	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint + Wood Veneer
20	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Stucco Paint
21	Reinforced concrete	3	Residential Commercial	Trade		Dwelling	Alçı+Fibercement

The material of the building facades is plain plastered, painted, coated facades, grandfather wood and fibercement coatings. Differentiations in the shape of the roof can be read as solution approaches brought by building heights and the shape of the parcel.

3.3. Evaluation of the structures in the study area with sustainable façade criteria.

Table 5: İstiklal Street-Sustainable façade criteria evaluation table of the examined buildings. Tabulated by the author, 2024.

İstasyon Caddesi - Çalışılan Yapıların Sürdürülebilir Cephe Kriterleri ile Değerlendirilmesi																									Toplam 56 puan	Yüzdeler (%)						
Hizmet Güneş Kontrolü				Ölçek / Kilit				Tarihî Sığartı Üçümlü ve Dışarı				Çatı Form Yaklaşım				Kendi Önerme ile Malzeme ve Teknik Yaklaşım				Kullanım				Toplam 56 puan			Yüzdeler (%)					
TOPIKORAFYA	RÜZGAR	GÜNEŞ	YERİŞ	YÜZGEÇLİK	SAÇAK BOYU	KÜTLE	PENCERE ORAN	KAPI ORAN	YAPI ÇEVRESİ	Düzenli Tarih	USLUP TEZATİĞİ	TAŞARIM BASSİRİNİ ÖZELİ	FORM	BALIKON	DEBİN BÖLÜMLERİ	ÇİTİPA	GRİ FAKSİL PAZ / ZENE	DEKÜ	RENK	KAPLAMA	İNSAN ÖLÇEĞİ	ZEMİN KAT SOKAK İZLİĞİ	SOKAK RİTİMİ					YOLLARA UYUMLU	Tarihî İletişim Paylaşım Uyumlu	YANARMA ÜZÜMLÜ	YANARMA ÜZÜMLÜ	YANARMA ÜZÜMLÜ
1	Bina 01	TESCİLLİ YAPI																														
2	Bina 02	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	1	1	0	2	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	22	39,29
3	Bina 03	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	14	25,00	
4	Bina 04	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	34	60,71	
5	Bina 05	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	35	62,50	
6	Bina 06	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	31	55,36		
7	Bina 07	TESCİLLİ YAPI																														
8	Bina 08	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	30	53,57	
9	Bina 09	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	0	1	2	2	2	1	2	0	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	39	69,64	
10	Bina 10	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	34	60,71	
11	Bina 11	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	48	85,71	
12	Bina 12	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	0	0	2	1	0	0	2	2	0	2	1	1	0	0	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	33	58,93	
13	Bina 13	TESCİLLİ YAPI																														
14	Bina 14	1	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	1	0	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	39	69,64	
15	Bina 15	1	1	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	26	46,43	
16	Bina 16	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	30	53,57	
17	Bina 17	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	35	62,50	
18	Bina 18	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	30	53,57	
19	Bina 19	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	37	66,07	
20	Bina 20	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	36	64,29	
21	Bina 21	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	29	51,79	
TOPLAM		50,0	50,0	55,6	47,2	86,1	86,1	83,3	44,4	33,3	22,2	77,8	61,1	55,6	55,6	52,8	16,7	55,6	52,8	47,2	44,4	63,9	63,9	63,9	61,1	72,2	61,1	66,7	86,1			
		18	18	20	17	31	31	30	16	12	8	28	22	20	20	19	6	20	19	17	16	23	23	23	22	26	22	24	31			

Figure 4: Graph showing the total percentages of sustainable façade criteria in new buildings. Prepared by the author, 2024.

Figure 5: Graph showing the percentages of sustainable façade criteria in new buildings. Prepared by the author, 2024.

Table 5 Value Definition of Injured New Building Design and Sustainable Facade Criteria

The evaluated criteria will be explained in the context of the study area in Köyiçi, Tuzla. Evaluation criteria 0,1,2 points will be accepted.

Score rating parameter;

0: Approach that has not been made or taken into account in the structure.

1: Approach that has been made in part and taken into account in part.

2: The approach that is made and taken into account

4. CONCLUSION and EVALUATION

In the conservation areas where historical buildings are located, there are many overlapping and contradictory criteria and parameters that affect the design of new buildings. For example, while the coincidence of the new building built next to the registered building with the registered building is not the right approach in terms of material and construction technique, the wooden cladding used on the façade of the building located further away harmonizes with the street silhouette. When we look at the critical value scores of the buildings given in Figure 4, the general evaluation is listed as follows.

If the evaluation is made on the 2 buildings with the lowest score; Building 1, It is seen that the structure built on top of the registered building (fountain) did not recede, did not bring the fountain to the fore and created a contradiction in the whole street, and at the same time, the dimensions of windows and doors were outside the general typology. The height of the building No. 2, which received the lowest score, the dimensions of the windows, the dimensions of the doors and showcases, the incompatibility of the façade cladding material in terms of sustainability and general texture are noteworthy.

Looking at the buildings with the best scores; It is seen that the building is close to 9 registered buildings, no traditional materials are used, the window

dimensions are in accordance with the typology and the eaves size is compatible.

In this context, it would not be wrong to conclude that; Proximity to the registered structure is 1 factor influencing the design of the new building, Window dimensions, material selection, height, eaves dimensions and all other criteria are gradually influencing.

At the same time, it would not be wrong to say that while the location criteria brought about by being away from the registered building allow for more free design, those responsible for the design do not approach according to the sustainability criteria, and they primarily apply the height elevations given by the municipalities they are affiliated with in terms of scale and mass criteria.

As a general conclusion and suggestion;

- New construction studies to be carried out in conservation areas should start with a good reading of the area, and the street silhouettes and typology studies of the area should be investigated or removed.

- The choice of material should be in harmony with the climatic conditions of the region and traditional material, but not of the same pattern, color and texture, and the registered façade of the building should not be copied.

- New buildings should be relegated as representation or their location on the street should be indicated by giving partial depth.

- Compliance with the typology should be taken into account when choosing window and door sizes that do not reduce the microclimate effect of the region.

- All ground floor showcases, doors and windows on Station Street, whose usage function is trade, should be designed by considering the street-human relationship.

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